

SILICONE IPN MODIFIED THERMOPLASTICS

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Silicone-hybrid polymer systems possess a desirable combination of mechanical, physiological, wear and release properties. A reactive processing method for producing substantially thermoplastic silicone semi-interpenetrating (pseudointerpenetrating) polymer network systems offers a practical cost effective route to these materials. Silicone-polyurethane, silicone-polyamide, and silicone-SEBS hybrids are the first examples.

The technology has been named Rimplast®. A simple statement of Rimplast® technology is as follows: Reactive silicone components are confined to separate solid pellets of matrix resin (e.g. urethane). The pellets are handled as a homogeneous mix. Upon entering the melt state in conventional injection molding or extrusion equipment the confinement of reactive silicones to individual pellets collapses and they begin to react with each other forming a pseudointerpenetrating polymer network. While it is essential that the reaction is initiated in the melt, it will proceed in the solid state. Within two to three hours of entering the melt state the property development associated with the formation of the IPN is substantially complete. Little or no difference between Rimplast® and conventional resin processing during extrusion or injection molding is observed. This is depicted in Figure 1.

Rimplast® technology represents a sequential semi-interpenetrating polymer network system generated by chemical cross-linking in the thermoplastic melt. This is a unique application of the IPN concept. Its potential should be readily distinguished by the user from traditional thermoset IPN systems and thermoplastics whose IPN character is only morphological and lack true cross-linking. A comparison of these general concepts in IPN technology is given in Figures 2 through 5. Figure 2 is a true IPN system in which two different polymer systems are crosslinked to themselves. The two networks interpenetrate each other. Figure 3 is a geometrical abstraction for Figure 2. One polymer is visualized in horizontal plane and the other is visualized in the vertical plane. The cross-linking is shown at the polymer chain termini. Polymers of Frisch are an example.¹ They are thermoset systems. In Figure 4 an apparent IPN is shown in which no cross-linking has taken place. The result is a system which is unstable and whose phases are independently extractable although the morphology resembles an IPN. Rimplast® semi-IPN or pseudo-IPN falls into a different category in which one polymer component is crosslinked as shown in Figure 5. The materials preserve thermoplastic character. Because the linear polymer is of high molecular weight, for all practical purposes, it is totally unextractable from the cross-

linked polymer. IPN's are usually hybrid polymer systems in which characteristics attributable to one of the polymers dominates in a particular function, consequently they are often considered with block copolymers. A geometrical abstraction of the block copolymers is shown in Figure 6. Although a different geometric axis is assigned to the blocks, they are in fact bound to each other in a linear arrangement making them thermoplastic. Like the apparent IPN's shown in Figure 4, they have morphological similarities to true and semi-IPNs.

Rimplast® technology is concerned specifically with a silicone IPN technology. One of the principal goals of this work was to translate certain desirable features of silicones including physiological, release, wear, and thermal properties into thermoplastics and thermoplastic elastomers. In order to do this, a chemistry was used which would not interfere with traditional melt processing properties. The chemistry of the process that generates the silicone IPN is a platinum-catalyzed vinyl-addition reaction, stated:

ADDITION VULCANIZATION OF POLYMER

This chemistry is adapted in a number of ways for specific polymer systems: The R substituents are varied to achieve an appropriate degree of compatibility with the matrix resin, the molecular weight and number of reactive groups are varied in order to achieve the desired cross-link density, and finally, the ratio of silicone to matrix polymer is varied.

The mechanical and physiological properties of IPN-modified silicone thermoplastics are compared to those of pure silicones and base polymers in Table 1. At a minimum, the mechanical properties of the matrix resin are preserved, and in many areas—including wear, lubricity, and abrasion resistance—they are improved. In high cross-link density systems the resilience and resistance to creep (set) of the resins is enhanced. The ready processability of these materials makes them good substitutes for liquid-injection-molded silicone.

